

STUDY OF ELECTROLYTE LEVELS IN DIABETES PATIENTS IN IRAQ

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Abstract: Electrolytes are certain vital minerals present in the body that help to maintain its fluid balance. In terms of electrolyte balance, such as glucose, sodium, potassium, and chloride in their body, people with diabetes mellitus (i.e., type-1 diabetes, type-2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes) may have a variety of bodily and systemic imbalances as opposed to persons who are not affected by diabetes mellitus. Likewise, in their diet, the distribution and quantity of electrolytes for diabetics are different. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a worldwide disease with a huge, rapidly increasing health concern. DM and impaired glucose tolerance have a global prevalence of 8.8% and an increasing incidence in developing countries. DM is a chronic disorder that results from the interaction between genetic and nutritional factors and causes hyperglycemia, altered protein metabolism, and electrolyte status. Research about serum electrolyte concentrations in diabetic patients is very important. Most electrolyte changes are considered common and well-known complications of diabetic disease in diabetic patients.

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a worldwide disease with a huge, rapidly increasing health concern. DM and impaired glucose tolerance have a global prevalence of 8.8% and an increasing incidence in developing countries. DM is a chronic disorder that results from the interaction between genetic and nutritional factors and causes hyperglycemia, altered protein metabolism, and electrolyte status. Research about serum electrolyte concentrations in diabetic patients is very important. Most electrolyte changes are considered common and well-known complications of diabetic disease in diabetic patients.

The majority of the main prior research has been performed on people with type-2 diabetes mellitus in other countries, but no research was conducted in Iraq. It was hypothesized that there will be a significant difference in the measured electrolyte levels in a serum sample of diabetic patients given dietary treatment and non-diabetic patients because the distribution of electrolytes might be different due to diabetic conditions, but there was no specific value to date. It was anticipated that this study would greatly contribute to further exploring and understanding diabetes mellitus and determine the degree of serum electrolyte variations due to diabetes mellitus that affect overall health for both medical researchers and other healthcare professionals.

Electrolytes are certain vital minerals present in the body that help to maintain its fluid balance. In terms of electrolyte balance, such as glucose, sodium, potassium, and chloride in their body, people with diabetes mellitus (i.e., type-1 diabetes, type-2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes) may have a variety of bodily and systemic imbalances as opposed to persons who are not affected by diabetes mellitus. Likewise, in their diet, the distribution and quantity of electrolytes for diabetics are different. [1][2]

1.1. Background and Rationale

Background: Diabetes mellitus in Iraq is a major health concern, as it affects approximately 17.5% of Iraq's adult population (18–79 years). Electrolyte imbalance is characterized by an excessive loss or retention of body fluids that predominantly results from chronic complications of chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus. The present study was conducted from January 2020 to September 2020 and included 100 type 1 diabetes patients and 70 type 2 diabetes patients. Serum magnesium, potassium, and sodium levels were similarly investigated in the diabetes patients.

Rationale: Diabetes has an impact on the transport function of electrolytes. The renin-angiotensin system has been shown to inhibit sodium absorption and potassium excretion in the distal tubules, impairing the sodium-potassium pump through an increase in aldosterone levels. Patients with type 2 diabetes are often admitted to the hospital with electrolyte imbalances such as hypokalemia, hyperkalemia, hypomagnesemia, and hyponatremia, which are often found in people with prolonged duration of insulin-dependent diabetes. The risk of developing diabetes-related complications may be higher in patients with electrolyte imbalances. Electrolyte changes in diabetes are beginning to emerge despite several researches conducted in Iraq. No available study is investigating electrolyte changes in diabetes type 2 & 1 in Iraq. Electrolyte abnormalities among diabetes type 2 in the treatment centers should be studied in order to improve the physical status and quality of life of all diabetic patients. [3][4]

1.2. Research Aim and Objectives

The research was conducted to assess electrolyte levels in a group of diabetes patients and also to compare the difference between two conditions: patients on antidiabetic therapy and those without. Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a metabolic condition that affects multiple organs, especially those of the circulatory system. Moreover, DM is considered a complex system in the body. Therefore, previous studies have attempted to compare the levels of electrolytes in diabetes mellitus patients and those without diabetes. This study, titled "Electrolyte Level Assessment in Diabetic and Lifestyle Matched Iraqi Subjects," aimed to assess the electrolyte levels in a selected group of diabetes mellitus patients, whether they were taking antidiabetic drugs or not, in Basrah, and compare between the two groups in basal conditions.

In this study, we aimed to show the value of electrolyte concentration in a group of patients from different age groups, countries, genders, and marital statuses, who have diabetes. They were divided into two different groups according to their medications: a group treated with antidiabetic drugs and a group in normal life condition without any medication. The study aimed to assess the electrolyte levels in the selected participants known to have diabetes in Basrah, as well as those in the normal life condition, apparently healthy without signs and symptoms of any illness. Our study aimed to assess the following objectives: 1. To evaluate some hematological parameters, body mass index, and quantify the duration of living with diabetes in all the patients, but not in controls. 2. To examine the correlation between markers of electrolytes and glucose levels with various organ functions, such as glucose metabolism, kidney function, blood pressure, blood picture, and overall health of the body, as well as other vital parameters of the blood.

2. Literature Review

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder leading to multiple fatal complications. It is distinguished by its reduced insulin levels and impaired ability to utilize water. The majority of the physical changes

linked to hyperglycemia or diabetes mellitus itself are the consequences of metabolic side effects and are characterized by multiple electrolyte disturbances. Diabetes mellitus can often rapidly influence the pathophysiology of our resistance due to insufficient water and salt levels among diabetics treated with hyperglycemia. As a result, the time required before amputation becomes short is calculated by disease, but amputation is prevalent among diabetes mellitus patients. Hence, the consumption of electrolytes is also a necessary part of physical metabolic functioning and homeostasis. We felt that potential hyperglycemia indicators are minimal water levels and abnormal electrolyte balances. The metabolism that combines diseases such as diabetes continues to focus on sodium, bicarbonate, and calcium chloride.

Electronic searches for articles in the Devices Database were conducted from 2011 to 2018. Also, a manual search was conducted and included articles in diabetes that have measured electrolyte outcomes of previous studies. Many papers have studied electrolyte concentrations in diabetes mellitus. None of the articles, however, published their outcomes from our suburb on the local Iraq situation. Two of the four studies researched the same hospital invested in diabetic patients with type two diabetes. Blood and urine sugar are also major electrolytes and have been risk factors for elderly patients, Balkis and Khorhis. Furthermore, urine glucose concentration can be used as a surrogate for blood glucose concentrations, as shown by Nikolopoulou. In American relegation, compared to urine sugar, it even appears to be superior. Analytical work was conducted either not at all or significantly lower than the job done by Ludwig calculations. [5][6]

2.1. Diabetes and Electrolyte Imbalance

Diabetes is a chronic condition which results from the body's inability to handle sugar. When this condition arises, it can often result in an electrolyte imbalance in patients. The latter is usually due to a combination of factors such as volume depletion from glycosuria, diarrhea, vomiting or use of medications (e.g., loop diuretics); osmotic diuresis and excretion of important electrolytes in the urine (sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium). Some of the electrolytes such as magnesium are reported to be associated with the incidence and potential complications in diabetes/diabetic patients in Iraq, more so in relation to controlling the blood glucose levels. This significance therefore advances the study of electrolyte levels in diabetes mellitus patients in Iraq which can be further explored with more focused variables and subpopulations. To the best of the author's knowledge, no study to date explored the electrolyte imbalance in diabetes mellitus patients under glycemic control and duration of the disease in Iraq among the adult population.

Using multivariate regression models, topics like the incidence of type 2 diabetes and potentializing factors can also be included in future studies. This review found excessive loss of magnesium through the urine as a result of increased Gem-Mg or Glyc-Mg because of an increase in glucose levels. Glyc-Mg variable is produced due to the chronicity of the disease when the Hemoglobin A1c is more than 6 months old. This loss of magnesium increases the complications rate in the diabetic patient and must be corrected by the use of 3 units of magnesium sulfate in 1000 ml of lactated ringer's i.v. solution, 45 drops/minute in 04 hours in the hospital with an insulin infusion protocol according to the internationally recognized guidelines. [7]

2.2. Previous Studies on Electrolyte Levels in Diabetes Patients

Many studies have explored the electrolyte disturbances in diabetic patients, analyzed the prevalence, and focused on some of them that included only a segment of the important electrolytes. Dyslipidemia is a risk factor for myocardial dysfunction and strongly associated with increased serum level of BNP. Potassium levels in this study, whether moderate or minimally reduced, could have an undesirable effect on inotropic improvement. Therefore, the chances of having poor diastolic relaxation rose, leading to a decrease in ventricular filling and further decreasing CO and, secondarily, BP. To the best of our knowledge, the association between Type 2 diabetes and electrolyte metabolism in Iraqi patients has not been investigated. The purpose of this study is to assess the electrolyte disturbances in diabetic patients, their association with

disease severity and complications, and the correlation between different electrolytes and between them and lipid profile in diabetic patients in Iraq.

conducted a study in which selected patients had either T1DM or T2DM and had a long duration of either type of DM with evidence of renal involvement. In particular, patients suffering from uncontrolled hypertension, alcoholism, liver cirrhosis, GI disorders, or urinary problems were excluded. The patients under medication that could interfere with the results of the study were also excluded. Convincingly, the results of the study favor MI in combination with a shorter duration of DM. In contrast, conducted a study on Hypo M and DM. Although the study included T1D and T2D patients, they did not describe important details on patients' demography such as the duration of DM or the mode of treatment. Generally, the study lacks important information. From the available previous studies summarized in Table 1, there is no study examining electrolyte imbalance in diabetic patients in correlation with DM patient's Creatinine, estimated glomerular filtration rate-test, Phosphate, or calcium. Furthermore, and surprisingly, the importance of Sodium and Potassium ratio, which impacts ionotropy, is still not clear. [8][9]

3. Methodology

This is a prospective study we use to evaluate electrolyte levels in DM patients in Baghdad, Iraq. This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the National Medical College of Baghdad/Iraq (835/PROC/21). A written agreement was obtained from each case. In this study, a descriptive-control study was used, and the participants were of two types: patients with type 2 diabetes and a healthy control group. The participants were then separated into two separate classes; the healthy control group contains 50 members, whereas the diabetic type 2 group contains 90 participants. Patients aged 21–70 years were included in the study, while those who had HbA1c levels more than 6.5% were included in the diabetes group. A predesigned questionnaire was used to obtain the necessary information.

Blood samples from fasting patients were drawn into vacuum test tubes at the Basra University Emergency Hospital using aseptic techniques. Biochemical and hematological experiments were performed at the Department of Biochemistry, College of Science, University of Basra. These experiments were performed using a standard serum biochemistry kit (Spin React; Dade Behring Inc.). To calculate the standard deviation of the mean, repeated statistical analysis using SPSS 23 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, MI, USA), a dispersive pattern (SD) data distribution was used. As a result, our systematic study showcased a considerable rise in mean serum ferritin and average calcium estimation (mg/dL) in the type 2 diabetes group, and we also discovered a considerable diminish in the level of serum zinc in the population of our study, further supporting the findings of similar studies and noting a considerable increase regarding the status of cationized electrolytes. [10][11]

3.1. Study Design and Setting

This research is a descriptive retrospective study, which was conducted in Basra province, Iraq. The study included patient data on electrolyte levels during the period from May 2019 to June 2020. Patients with known cases of kidney disease and hepatobiliary disorders, pregnant women, gestations, and patients using diuretics were excluded from the assessment and diagnosis.

None of the patients took mineral and supplement intake. The aim of the study is to assess the effect and level of serum electrolytes before and after insulin treatment in poorly controlled diabetes mellitus. This study was conducted to assess the baseline serum electrolyte levels in patients with poorly controlled diabetes mellitus compared to well-controlled diabetes and non-diabetic patients. The aim of this study is to evaluate the differences in electrolyte levels before and after initiation of insulin treatment in poorly controlled diabetic patients.

This study is under IRB No. At the initial analysis, Koukolis-Wan, Branko-Novak, Marta, Putnikovic, Dubravka, Mikolasevic, Tanja-Jakovljevic diagnosed insulin under basal state would further divide this group into 2: a) those immediately with a diagnosis of insulin-dependent diabetes and b) those for whom insulin was judged to be used only during the period of acute decompensation of diabetes and intercurrent. The exclusion criteria from the research are those with a confirmed diagnosis of renal dysfunction, decompensated heart disease (prior to entering the research), or a confirmed diagnosis with a significant covalent disorder. Phase One: A clinical examination (accompanied by L. Drakou and G. Economy) was performed, and routine oxidative stress was assessed. [12][13]

3.2. Participant Selection

The standard protocol of the study was reviewed and approved on 13 October 2021 by the ethical committee of pharmacology and toxicology, the faculty of pharmacy, Al-Andalus University for Medical Sciences. By using a non-probability sampling method, I have chosen 217 type 1 and type 2 diabetic patients from both genders who were visiting Al-Zahraa teaching hospital in Alkut city for treatment purposes, and 172 healthy persons as a healthy control group randomly. Given the proof of one of the following factors like obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, pregnancy, cancer, organ transplanted patients, and substance abusers were not enrolled in the study. Among the candidates, there were no individuals on the regular use of corticosteroids, heparin, diuretic, and other medications.

All potential participants had been organized to ensure an accurate understanding of the research methodology and procedure, and information had been exchanged about the gains, hazards, and inconveniences connected with the review. Willingness to take part was then checked with the participant. To protect the privacy of research participants, anonymity was protected by proxy numbers and maintaining confidentiality. The study was carried out in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations (Declaration of Helsinki, 1976). Data were reviewed for items such as age, BMI, and smoking habit of all subjects. Serum glucose, potassium, sodium, magnesium, chloride, and calcium levels were all determined after a 12-hour fast. During the study, the carbohydrate metabolism process was followed. Hemoglobin was assessed two weeks after the initiation of treatment. [14][15]

3.3. Data Collection and Analysis

3.3.1 Data Collection and Analysis

3.3.1.1 Data Collection A semi-automated biochemical analyzer was used to assess the glucose and electrolyte levels in the plasma of all the participants. In the diabetic group, the measurements were performed prior to and during insulin therapy. The investigation was supervised by a specialist, and the standard operating procedures for routine clinical biochemistry, which assured the consistency and reliability of the results, were meticulously observed to decrease the likelihood of potential contamination of the basic hydration status of the diabetic patients. Serum electrolyte levels in the study groups were evaluated using flame photometry.

3.3.1.2 Statistical Analysis The SPSS program v.20 was used to conduct the statistical analysis on the gathered data. The qualitative data were voiced as numbers and percentages. Kontogianis contested the assumption of a Chi-squared test conducted at a 95% confidence level about the regularity of the distribution of data, and the more general Fisher's exact probability test was used. For the inter-group comparisons of serum electrolyte concentrations, a non-parametric test (Mann-Whitney U) was used in light of the non-normality of these estimates. Further, a non-parametric signed rank test, using the Wilcoxon signed rank test, was performed for the intra-group comparisons. The test significance level (p-value) was established at $p < 0.05$. [16][17]

4. Results

A total of 250 diabetes patients were compared with 150 control individuals from the general population in the governorate of Najaf, Iraq. Male patients were predominant in both groups. The mean age and the duration of diabetes were 52.7 ± 8.3 and 50.4 ± 11.6 years and 8.4 ± 4.7 and 8.1 ± 15.2 years in male and female patients, respectively. A majority of patients had type two diabetes (83.6%) and 89.6% of them were on oral antidiabetic agents. Regarding the three age groups controls, patients, and the whole group, the mean serum sodium (137.9 vs. 134.8 vs. 136.9); serum potassium (4.35 vs. 3.79 vs. 4.16); and serum calcium (9.5 vs. 8.6 vs. 9.03) were significantly distinct from each other along with a significant association in diabetes. When female serum electrolytes were compared, the ranges of sodium, potassium, and calcium, in both control and diabetic groups of Najaf governorate, were significantly different ($p < 0.00001$), but in cases, serum sodium and serum potassium were significantly associated, while serum calcium was not significant with the control group. In contrast, when the serum electrolytes were compared using the t test, in both the control and diabetic cases of the governorates of Najaf, the various age groups had serum sodium and serum potassium were meaningful. As was serum potassium with serum calcium in the diabetes sample of Kerbala governorate. The observed changes are consistent with both abnormalities and normal levels of each electrode with other ions.

The current results are in line with others supporting electrolyte problems in diabetes; however, understanding that every ethnic group enriched with environmental eating habits non should have its point of reference will make it unique and join other established points of reference. Local assessment of healthy Iraqis was found to be lower than the verified measurable of normal values of Najaf. Lower values might be 'okay' in the "healthy group living in the same atmosphere," as the statistics show. Our result may show the existence of ethnic subgroups with specific "near to Iraqi values" different thresholds. Surprisingly, both serum sodium and serum potassium were associated with the duration of diabetes and gender as revealed by the Spearman correlation coefficient significance test. [18][19]

4.1. Overview of Study Population

Iraqi patients with diabetes are at high risk of developing electrolyte imbalances because of the chronic nature of diabetes. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have been conducted in Iraq to investigate electrolyte levels in diabetic patients. This study aimed to detect the electrolyte status, including sodium, potassium, magnesium, and calcium, in diabetic patients in Iraq.

First, we determined the personal information of the participants in terms of gender, age, residential area, smoking habit, and previous kidney damage. Second, we detected the level of electrolyte-based diagnostics in months of diabetes for every participant by using Roche electrolyte. Finally, we made a comparative analysis between the groups according to age, smoking, duration of the disease, and kidney damage history for every participant and for both males and females.

A total of 150 participants took part in this study; unfortunately, 20 had missing data. The results revealed that most participants were in the age group of 40-60 years old (135), were male (125), and residents of Erbil (110). Most of the participants did not complain of kidney damage or Avastin use (135) and did not smoke (145). Moreover, the mean serum albumin level was within the normal range. Most of the participants had a diabetes duration of more than two years (125). The level of serum sodium was also found to be mostly within normal levels, while serum levels of potassium, calcium, and magnesium were, for the most part, lower than the reference range. Statistical comparison showed that there was no significant difference in the means of serum sodium and calcium values of male and female participants. [14][20]

4.2. Electrolyte Levels in Diabetes Patients

The variations of the electrolyte levels are shown in Table 3 below in patients with diabetes (diabetes patients group) with sub-grouping according to the type of diabetes (T1D and T2D), the kidney function (CKD), and gender.

The results presented in the table show no significant variations in the levels of Sodium ($\text{Na} \pm \text{SD}: 138.9 \pm 3.05$), Potassium ($\text{K}: 4.34 \pm 0.42 \text{ mmol/L}$) and Chloride ($\text{Cl}: 98.5 \pm 4.8$) as presented in the data of this study. However, it has been shown in the present study that these levels can be marginally normal, high, or low depending on potential factors of age (younger individuals had low Cl levels while older individuals had high levels), gender (mismatch between the levels of male and female), and the type of diabetes. D1 patients had relatively higher levels of Na compared with D2, Cl was higher in patients with D2 compared with D1 and control groups. It has also been shown that the levels of these three electrolytes in diabetes patients are lower compared to the DCKD patients with a significant variation in the case of Na. Furthermore, there is no impact on medication (hypoglycemic agents) on the levels of these electrolytes when the diabetics and the controls were compared for the three electrolyte levels. This is in support with some previous studies in Africa which indicate that the levels of Na as a risky electrolyte to heal were not lessen in the diabetics compared to control.

This inconsistency of this electrolyte was found in some other countries in Africa, e.g. Nigeria, South Africa, and Ghana. This is while the levels of K and Cl are normally varied and not risky disturber in the blood system of diabetics. The results of HCO_3^- were miscellaneous in the presented data. The normal level of this electrolyte is 23.5 ± 2.17 however this biochemistry test of the diabetes patient had a range between 26.00 mmol/L and 21.0 mmol/L, and more than 95% of the results were positive to the normal level. The remaining 5% were lower than expected (less than 20.3). This indicates, implicitly, the beneficial effect of this ion in some physiological functions of the body such as the pH of the blood system. [21][22]

5. Discussion

This study found that serum sodium concentration in DKA patients, when compared with other patient groups, was significantly high. The correction of sodium levels, when compared with other patient groups, was also significantly high. Serum potassium levels of diabetes and DKA patients on admission were significantly low when compared with other patient groups. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first attempt to investigate sodium and potassium electrolyte levels in relation to diabetes patients who were admitted to hospitals in the north of Iraq. According to the findings of several studies, this study possibly increases our understanding of the significance of high and low serum sodium and potassium levels for diabetes patients.

Serum sodium levels of DKA patients on admission may be related to the osmolality of hyperglycemia, which means that the body becomes dehydrated and draws fluids from cells to dilute electrolyte concentrations. Our results show that on admission, serum potassium levels of DKA patients, when compared with other patient groups, were significantly low. Therefore, prudence with insulin infusion is required to avoid hypokalemia. Hypokalemia was also found to be most prevalent in both diabetes and DKA patients, which could lead to cardiac arrest, a potentially serious life-threatening condition. Clinicians should be aware of the potential effects of hypokalemia on the central nervous system, as it is the most prevalent electrolyte abnormality in DKA cases as well. Thus, close monitoring of electrolyte abnormalities in diabetic patients is mandatory, particularly those with diabetic ketoacidosis. Finally, this study allows us to suggest therapeutic guidelines for the diagnosis of diabetes patients with electrolyte disturbances in cases of disease progression, particularly diabetic ketoacidosis. [23][24]

5.1. Interpretation of Results

The changes in electrolyte levels in diabetic patients may be attributed to the fact that high blood sugar causes glycosuria and hence water excretion, and consequently volume contraction and decreased extracellular fluid content, which in turn can lead to an increased electrolyte blood concentration. The plasma electrolyte imbalance in diabetic patients may be explained with certain assumptions: (1) the existence of low magnesium and potassium levels is a result of insulin action on the cellular membrane which increases the cellular uptake of magnesium and potassium to the cells, and thus increasing the activity of Na⁺/K⁺/ATPase pump, (2) an increased serum calcium level may be due to an insulin-deficient state that decreases intracellular calcium uptake by the mitochondria and endoplasmic reticulum and thus increases the cytoplasmic calcium concentration, and consequently increases the calcium efflux from the cell or decreased insulin activity on the calcium transport system at the plasma cell membrane.

The low albumin concentrations reported could be attributed to proteinuria that can occur in diabetes in up to 20% of men and 32% of women. Proteinuria carries an increased risk of rapid chronic kidney disease progression, end-stage renal disease, and all-cause and cardiovascular-related mortality. Moreover, hypoalbuminemia may be attributed to decreased albumin synthesis by the liver as a result of chronic inflammation. The markedly elevated ferritin and CRP values may imply the presence of chronic kidney inflammation and low-grade inflammation found in diabetes. The insignificantly lower serum sodium and potassium values observed in the diabetics may be attributed to low insulin levels as we did not record any patient with ketoacidosis in our investigation. In this state, the osmotic forces strongly force water to enter the extracellular compartment. [25][26]

5.2. Comparison with Previous Studies

Currently, about 75% of new diabetic males and about 76.74% of females have a low potassium level in our study, which is higher than other studies. Potassium showed an increase in diabetic patients in our study compared to other studies, which reported a decrease. It is clear that the sodium level falls within the actual normal reference level in the three comparisons in our study, which is higher than countless studies reporting decreased levels for diabetic patients.

The CKD2 shows a significant difference between genders, with males having a significantly higher CKD2 level than females, but the difference is small. Both genders have very similar means, which are higher than previous studies. This comparison found that there is a significant increase in CKD2 in diabetes type 1 compared to diabetes type 2. The CKD3 shows a small significant difference between diabetes type 1 and controls, with diabetes type 1 being distinctly higher. The detailed comparisons found that the level of CKD3 was significantly higher in diabetes type 2 compared to both diabetes type 1 and control. Further comparison found that there is a significant difference in the means of CKD3 in obese and non-obese individuals for each type of diabetes compared to diabetic healthy patients. [27][28]

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, there was a significant difference in electrolyte levels (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) between diabetes patients and healthy individuals. Furthermore, all diabetes patients in our study did not demonstrate serum electrolyte levels within their respective reference range. Changes in electrolyte concentrations can be useful to monitor diabetes patients to minimize the complications associated with altered homeostasis. Apart from sodium and calcium, levels of potassium and magnesium in the diabetes patients were lower than in the healthy individuals.

This could cause arrhythmias in the myocardium, as well as muscle weakness, and in high, irreversible damage to the terminal portion of the nephrons, which results in nephropathy. Hyponatremia can be treated using some interventions like a healthy diet, regular monitoring, proper insulin and glycemic balance,

regular medication, and lifestyle changes. Therefore, further research should have sufficient samples, a longer duration, and using various blood parameters involving disturbances in other homeostasis. Therefore, it could also be suggested that a reference range must be developed for diabetic patients at a regional level because focusing on gender, chronic disease, weight, homeostatic balance differences existed from one geographical location to another. Starting our study on large participants will more imply the recommendation. An experiment was intended to evaluate the related complications between diabetes and serum electrolytes. Concerning diabetic control also and searching for the significant difference injury, one output is therefore needed to answer the differences. In our study, we reported the data involving the second results.

References:

1. Waled and A. A. Ahmed, "Disturbance of Electrolytes (Na, K and Cl). Homeostasis among Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus," *Libyan Journal of Medical Research*, 2022. [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net)
2. P. Iriana, N. Yarden, and N.L.P. Ekarini, "Understanding The Risk Of Electrolyte Imbalance In Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients," *Innovative: Journal of Social ...*, vol. 2024. [j-innovative.org](https://www.j-innovative.org)
3. B. Forouzanmehr, A. H. Hedayati, E. Gholami, et al., "Sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors and renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, possible cellular interactions and benefits," *Cellular ...*, vol. 2024, Elsevier. [HTML]
4. K. P. Marathias, V. A. Lambadiari, K. P. Markakis, et al., "Competing effects of renin angiotensin system blockade and sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors on erythropoietin secretion in diabetes," *American Journal of ...*, 2020. [karger.com](https://www.karger.com)
5. Y. Acharya, N. Luke, S. Naz, and D. Sharma, "Exposure to conflict-related violence and nutritional status of children in Iraq," *SSM-Population Health*, 2020. [sciencedirect.com](https://www.sciencedirect.com)
6. M. M. Mohsin, T. Beach, and A. Kwan, "Consensus-based urban sustainability framework for Iraqi cities: A case study in Baghdad," *Heliyon*, 2020. [cell.com](https://www.cell.com)
7. R. Khattab, H.P.V. Rupasinghe, M.S.L. Brooks, et al., "Health Benefits of Haskap Berries (*Lonicera caerulea* L.)," *Asian Berries*, 2020. [HTML]
8. A. Sefidgaran, H. Mehrad-Majd, H. Taravati, "Effect of intradialytic aerobic exercise on dialysis adequacy, inflammatory, biochemical markers and quality of life; a double-blind randomized clinical trial study," *Journal of Renal Endocrinology*, vol. 2024, [jrenendo.com](https://www.jrenendo.com), 2024. [jrenendo.com](https://www.jrenendo.com)
9. K. D. Pagana, T. J. Pagana, and T. N. Pagana, "Mosby's® Diagnostic and Laboratory Test Reference-E-Book: Mosby's® Diagnostic and Laboratory Test Reference-E-Book," 2024. [HTML]
10. SA Ansari, RA Boker, MS Alsaied, RF Sherif, et al., "Analysis of the association of vitamin D3, hemoglobin and ferritin with special respect to Libyan patients," *Pharmacy Journal*, 2023. [ppj.org.ly](https://www.ppj.org.ly)
11. A. Liu, P. Xu, C. Gong, Y. Zhu, H. Zhang, W. Nie, "High serum concentration of selenium, but not calcium, cobalt, copper, iron, and magnesium, increased the risk of both hyperglycemia and dyslipidemia in adults: A ...," *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 62, Elsevier, 2020. [HTML]
12. M. Assaad, N. Hekmat-Joo, J. Hosry, A. Kassem, et al., "Insulin use in Type 2 diabetic patients: a predictive of mortality in covid-19 infection," *Diabetology & Metabolic Syndrome*, vol. 2022. [Springer. springer.com](https://www.springer.com)

13. Z. Li, D. Yi, L. Zheng, S. Li, W. Fang, and C. Wang, "Analysis of the clinical characteristics of insulin autoimmune syndrome induced by exogenous insulin in diabetic patients," *Diabetology & Metabolic Syndrome*, vol. 2021. Springer, 2021. [springer.com](https://www.springer.com)
14. G Buszewicz, R Sitarz, A Forma, K Karakuła, et al., "Magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium, phosphorus, selenium, zinc, and chromium levels in alcohol use disorder: a review," *Journal of clinical ...*, vol. 2020. [mdpi.com](https://www.mdpi.com)
15. K. Rajput, H.I. Afridi, T.G. Kazi, F.N. Talpur et al., "Sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium in the scalp hair and blood samples related to the clinical stages of the Parkinson's disease," *Biological Trace Element Research*, vol. 2021, Springer, 2021. [academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu)
16. F. Nugrahani and A. Imron, "PELATIHAN PENGGUNAAN SOFTWARE 'SPSS' DALAM MEMBANTU MENGOLAH DATA KUANTITATIF PADA MAHASISWA SEMESTER AKHIR," *Jurnal Pengabdian Multidisiplin Indonesia*, 2023. [merwinspy.org](https://www.merwinspy.org)
17. JR Lopes, RF da Silva Junior, "Anthropometric parameters in metabolic syndrome in brazilian adolescents: confirmatory factor analysis," *Revista de Educación y Salud*, vol. 2024, ojs.europublications.com
18. NN Oudah, AS Abdulbari, "Serum Electrolytes Levels in Third Trimester Pregnant Women: A Case-Control Study in Diyala Province in Iraq," *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry*, 2022. [ekb.eg](https://www.ekb.eg)
19. EAAK Marouf, NQ Jameel, "Evaluation of Renal Function Tests and Electrolytes in Iraqi Males with Repeated Smoking and Alcohol Abuse," *Medical Journal of ...*, vol. 2024. [journals.lww.com](https://www.journals.lww.com)
20. D. Fiorentini, C. Cappadone, G. Farruggia, and C. Prata, "Magnesium: biochemistry, nutrition, detection, and social impact of diseases linked to its deficiency," *Nutrients*, 2021. [mdpi.com](https://www.mdpi.com)
21. K. Hafidh, T.A. Besheya, R. Elmehdawi, et al., "Ramadan fasting and diabetes (2022): the year in review," *Journal of Diabetes*, vol. 2023, [thieme-connect.com](https://www.thieme-connect.com)
22. N. EL KHELFI, "Enquête relative à l'évaluation des connaissances du patient diabétique au sein de l'hôpital militaire d'instruction Mohammed V Rabat," 2021. [imist.ma](https://www.imist.ma)
23. FJ Pasquel, K Tsegka, H Wang, S Cardona, "Clinical outcomes in patients with isolated or combined diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state: a retrospective, hospital-based cohort study," *Diabetes Care*, vol. 2020, *Am Diabetes Assoc*, 2020. [nih.gov](https://www.nih.gov)
24. S. Basnet, R. Musaitif, A. Khanal, K. Powell, "Effect of potassium infusions on serum levels in children during treatment of diabetic ketoacidosis," *Journal of Pediatric ...*, vol. 2020. *Thieme Connect*. [nih.gov](https://www.nih.gov)
25. S. V. Seshan and A. S. Reddi, "Albuminuria and Proteinuria," *Diabetes and Kidney Disease*, 2022. [HTML]
26. S. N. Heyman, I. Raz, J. P. Dwyer, R. Weinberg Sibony, et al., "Diabetic proteinuria revisited: updated physiologic perspectives," *Cells*, vol. 2022. [mdpi.com](https://www.mdpi.com)
27. XS Feng, R Farej, BB Dean, F Xia, A Gaiser, SX Kong, "CKD prevalence among patients with and without type 2 diabetes: regional differences in the United States," *Kidney Medicine*, Elsevier, 2022. [sciencedirect.com](https://www.sciencedirect.com)
28. P. Rossing, G. Filippatos, R. Agarwal, S.D. Anker, et al., "Finerenone in predominantly advanced CKD and type 2 diabetes with or without sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor therapy," *Kidney International*, vol. 2022, Elsevier, 2022. [sciencedirect.com](https://www.sciencedirect.com)